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**ORGANIZING TECHNOLOGY LESSONS BASED ON BLENDED LEARNING
TECHNOLOGY**

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Annotation: This article covers the theoretical and practical foundations of effective organization of technology lessons based on the Blended Learning approach, which is widely used among modern pedagogical technologies. Blended learning serves to deepen students' knowledge and form independent thinking by combining traditional and digital (online) teaching methods.

Keywords: Blended learning, Blended Learning, digital education, competence, pedagogical technology, online and traditional education.

Introduction.

The innovative development of the education system in the 21st century requires the introduction of modern pedagogical approaches. In this regard, Blended Learning technology is recognized as an important structural element of the educational process in optimizing the educational process, ensuring individualized education, and forming student competencies. This technology is based on the integration of traditional (audience-based) and distance (digital) teaching methods, and encourages students to acquire independent knowledge, critical and systematic thinking, as well as active participation in innovative projects.

The blended learning model is organized in pedagogical activities based on such didactic components as a constructivist approach, differentiated teaching, adapted educational resources, and an interactive environment. In this process, the student becomes not a passive participant in acquiring knowledge, but an active subject, that is, an active performer of educational activities. In particular, the specificity of the science of technology - practical exercises, development of engineering thinking, and project-based work - makes the Blended Learning approach especially relevant and effective for this subject.

Today, the use of digital platforms (Google Classroom, Moodle, Microsoft Teams, Edmodo, etc.), video lessons, online laboratories, virtual constructors and other interactive tools in organizing technology lessons creates an opportunity to form modern professional skills in students, as well as develop their digital literacy. Therefore, this article analyzes on a scientific basis the methodological approaches to organizing technology lessons based on Blended Learning technology, their forms of integration with pedagogical and information and communication technologies, as well as their role in the formation of students' personal and professional competencies.

Transformational processes in the education system, especially in the post-pandemic period, have required the widespread introduction of digital tools into the educational process. As a result, Blended Learning technology has begun to be

recognized not only as a temporary solution, but also as a sustainable approach to improving the quality of education. This approach is of particular importance in teaching technology, since this subject is based on the integral unity of theoretical and practical knowledge.

Blended Learning encompasses several basic models, including:

Rotation Model – Students rotate between different formats such as traditional classes, online activities, hands-on work, and project work over a period of time. In technology, this model is particularly useful for project-based learning.

Flex Model – the main part of the lesson is organized online, and the teacher provides individual and group assistance. This model creates ample opportunities for independent learning for the student.

Enriched Virtual Model – online learning plays the main role, but face-to-face meetings are held from time to time. This model is convenient for testing practical skills.

In accordance with the content of the technological subject, Blended Learning technology is implemented based on the following components:

Formation of a digital learning environment: virtual classrooms are organized for lessons on platforms such as Google Classroom, Edmodo, Moodle. Assignments, tests, and educational materials are posted through these platforms.

Video lessons and animations: explanations are provided using video materials on technological processes (drawing, mechanisms, materials processing technology) provided for in textbooks.

Practical tasks are performed through virtual laboratories: for example, graphic work and design work are performed using programs such as AutoCAD or SketchUp.

Feedback and assessment: students' activities are assessed online using tools such as Google Forms, Quizizz, Kahoot. Formative and summative assessment types are used.

As a result of using Blended Learning technology, the following competencies are formed in students:

Information and communication competence: the student learns to independently use digital resources, search for and analyze relevant technological information.

Project competence: innovative thinking and solution development skills are developed through independent and group project-based tasks in technology lessons.

Professionally oriented competence: career guidance and practical work skills are strengthened by working on real-life issues.

In the Blended Learning process, the teacher's role is more of a guide, advisor, and coordinator than a knowledge provider. The teacher monitors the online activities of students, provides assistance based on an individual approach, and

relies on fair criteria for assessment.

Analysis and discussion:

Scientific and theoretical research and practical experience on the implementation of Blended Learning technology in modern education show that this approach is effective not only in consolidating students' knowledge, but also in ensuring their active participation in the learning process. In particular, the implementation of this model in technology lessons has yielded positive results in the following areas: While traditional teaching methods prioritize a more frontal approach, in the Blended Learning approach, the student receives education at the pace of his own personal mastery. This creates the basis for the practical application of the principles of a differentiated approach. For example, a student can review topics that are incomprehensible to him through an online platform and complete independent tasks individually. This increases the quality of mastery.

Since the content of technology is mainly focused on practice, it is not enough to provide only theoretical knowledge during the lesson. Through the Blended Learning model, students will have the opportunity to practically consolidate theoretical knowledge using virtual laboratories, digital drawings, and animated videos. This method is also an important factor in developing students' creativity, problem-solving, and project thinking skills. While in traditional lessons the role of the teacher as a source of knowledge is dominant, in blended learning a constructive, two-way dialogue is formed between the student and the teacher. The teacher's prompt feedback on the tasks given on online platforms, individual advice, and assistance through additional resources stimulate student activity. This, in turn, serves to form metacognitive competencies. The effective implementation of Blended Learning technology largely depends on the teacher's digital literacy, pedagogical design, integration of educational technologies, educational analysis, and assessment skills. Therefore, in-depth training in the basics of Blended Learning is of great importance in the system of retraining and advanced training of pedagogical personnel. Also, the analysis shows that the technical base (computers, Internet speed, interactive platforms) and the digital infrastructure of educational institutions play a decisive role in the successful implementation of Blended Learning technology. Otherwise, the possibility of fully utilizing the capabilities of this technology may be limited. Therefore, before organizing technology lessons in a blended format, it is necessary to analyze the technical support of schools and the availability of digital tools among students.

Conclusion.

Blended Learning technology is one of the important innovative directions of the modern education system, which serves to optimize the learning process through the effective integration of traditional and digital forms of education. Research shows that the application of this technology to technology subjects not only deepens students' theoretical knowledge, but also gives significant results in the formation of practical skills, independent thinking, project work and the

development of digital competencies. Technology lessons organized on the basis of the Blended Learning model:

create a personalized learning environment taking into account the pace of students' learning;

help to deepen understanding of educational materials through interactive and multimedia resources;

form creative thinking, problem-solving and professional competencies;

give the teacher a new methodological role as the main guide of the educational process.

Therefore, the widespread introduction of Blended Learning technology in technology lessons is one of the most relevant tools for increasing students' interest in learning, improving the quality of education and training qualified personnel in line with the real requirements of the labor market.

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